

**Report of Research Assessment Practices at Blanquerna, URL
in the last 20 years: 2004-2024**

*CoARA pilot project
Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE),
Blanquerna – Universitat Ramon Llull*

*December, 2025
Version 2.0*

Report of Research Assessment Practices at Blanquerna (Universitat Ramon Llull) in the last 20 years: 2004-2024.

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December, 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101131826

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1. Review of Current Practices

1.1. Background

The Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE) has a long-standing tradition of evaluating the research activity of its academic staff, beginning with the publication of its first evaluation criteria and procedures in October 2004.

Evaluation—covering both teaching and research—is structured in three-year cycles. The first evaluation covered the period from September 2004 to August 2007, although internal circumstances delayed its actual implementation.

The process was reactivated following the May 2010 publication of the institutional framework for academic career progression. The evaluation period was extended to September 2010, and the assessment focused exclusively on faculty members with officially recognised research time in their contracts. In 2010, 58 faculty members were assessed: 51% received a positive evaluation, 30% negative evaluation, and 19% did not submit the required documentation.

In March 2013, a second round of evaluations was conducted using the same criteria, with an exemption introduced for those who had already undergone external evaluation by a recognised quality agency (e.g., doctoral defence, academic accreditation, or recognised research periods). Of the 69 eligible faculty members, 56% were evaluated positively, 22% negatively, and 22% were exempt. Additional evaluations were conducted in 2016 and 2019, maintaining similar procedures and yielding comparable results.

1.2. Unified Evaluation Criteria

In preparation for the 2024–2029 General Research Plan (*Pla General de recerca*- PGR) uniting the three Blanquerna faculties, a joint reflection process was initiated on how to evaluate academic research activity. While FPCEE had previously conducted four rounds of evaluation, the faculties of Health Sciences and of Communication and International Relations had not. The process began by reviewing other universities' models. It was designed to align with the qualitative and quantitative standards used by quality assurance agencies to evaluate researchers and research centres in Catalonia and Spain. The primary goal was to establish common evaluation standards across the three faculties, while respecting the specificity of their academic disciplines.

Development Process

The work began in February 2021 with the Vice-Deans of Research from all three faculties. A preliminary draft was shared with the Directors of Research Institutes, amended accordingly, and then submitted for approval by the Blanquerna Research and Ethics Council (*Comissió d'Ètica i Recerca-CER*).

Though the PGR was not formally approved until January 2024, the CER agreed to pilot the new evaluation system at FPCEE in 2023, continuing the established three-year cycle. The pilot covered the period from October 1, 2019, to September 30, 2022. This pilot helped calibrate scoring thresholds for each contractual academic profile across faculties. Prior to launching the pilot, all research group leaders at the faculty were briefed to clarify the new criteria. Once validated, the evaluation system was also implemented at the other two faculties.

Evaluation as a Quality Indicator

Research and quality are intrinsically linked. Research enhances methodological rigour, while quality assessment ensures that scientific production is appropriate and recognised. For the most recent evaluation, the process was jointly implemented by the Research Office and the Faculty's Quality Unit to ensure alignment with the evaluation of teaching activities traditionally managed by the latter.

Purpose of the Evaluation

The assessment targeted faculty members with officially recognised research time. It aimed to stimulate research activity, support career development strategies, and maintain quality standards required by external agencies. Two secondary goals emerged:

- The need to provide evidence helped to uncover achievements not previously reported through regular channels (e.g., the MERIT platform or research funding tracking).
- The validation process allowed for pedagogical correction of misreported records.

The evaluation tool was also designed as a self-assessment instrument, allowing academics to measure their research achievements against their professional category's expectations, even though formal evaluations will continue to follow the three-year cycle.

Evaluation Criteria

The assessment was based on three categories:

- *Productivity* (60% weight): Impact-factor publications (JCR, SJR), books or chapters (SPI), other publications, dissemination activities (conference presentations, peer review, editorial boards), and contributions like doctoral supervision and patents.
- *Projects* (35%): Leadership or participation in competitive and non-competitive projects, with recognition also given to unsuccessful competitive proposals.
- *Other merits* (5%): Research group leadership and research stays (minimum one month).

A standardised form was created to collect personal data, quantitative metrics for each category, and qualitative tables to support the submitted evidence. Guidelines and templates accompanied the call.

Validation Process

Evaluation was also intended as a formative exercise. Alongside scores, individualised feedback addressed issues in the submitted evidence. Validation was supported by technical staff from the Library Service (publications), Research Office (research projects), and Innovation and Transfer Office (transfer projects). A shared validation spreadsheet facilitated annotations and corrections.

Results

Only faculty members with recognised research time were required to participate; others could opt in voluntarily. A differentiated scoring threshold was applied based on contract type. In the latest call, 80 researchers participated, with 20% exempt due to external evaluation credentials. Of the remaining 64, 43% received a “very favorable” evaluation, 42% “favorable,” and 14% “unfavorable.”

Feedback

Each researcher received personalised feedback via email, including:

- Overall rating (very favourable, favourable, or not favourable)
- Score out of 100
- Average and score range for their academic category
- The scoring table for each evaluation parameter

Where applicable, feedback included detailed explanations of corrections and contact details for follow-up with the validating departments.

1.3. Documents and Tools Used

- Annex 1. Call for applications
- Annex 2. Evaluation form template
- Annex 3. Table completion guide
- Annex 4. Scoring table with categories, parameters, metrics, values, and caps
- Annex 5. Final scoring thresholds
- Annex 6. Individual evaluation report template

2. Assessment of Current Research Assessment Practices

2.1. Strengths

1. Institutionalisation and Continuity

- A long-standing tradition of regular, structured evaluations (since 2004) has institutionalised assessment as part of academic culture.
- The triennial cycle provides a consistent framework for faculty career development and accountability.

2. *Structured and Transparent Procedures*

- Defined criteria communicated through templates and guides ensure conceptual transparency.
- Clear communication through individualised feedback and engagement of technical services ensures procedural transparency.

3. *Integration of Quality Assurance Structures*

- Collaboration between the Research Office and the Quality Unit strengthens coherence between teaching and research evaluations.

4. *Recent Moves Towards Unification and Reflection*

- Efforts to develop unified criteria across all faculties reflect institutional commitment to improving consistency.

5. *Formative aim of the research evaluation*

- Feedback mechanisms offer developmental support for researchers, including correction of misreported evidence and learning opportunities.

2.2. Weaknesses

1. *Heavy Dependence on Quantitative Indicators*

- A heavy reliance on bibliometric criteria (JCR/SJR, IF) and competitive funding metrics reinforces a productivity-based culture, contrary to CoARA principles.

2. *Limited Recognition of Diverse Contributions*

- Other forms of impact (societal, collaborative, open science practices) are marginal or missing in the current framework.

3. *Rigid Scoring Model*

- Top-down metrics (fixed scores, caps) may not accommodate disciplinary diversity or career-stage differences, potentially disadvantaging early-career researchers or interdisciplinary work.

4. *Partial Coverage*

- Only researchers with officially recognised research hours are evaluated mandatorily. This may exclude relevant contributions from other academics, hindering a holistic understanding of the institution's research landscape.

5. *Limited Peer Involvement and Reflective Dialogue*

- While technical validation is robust, there is little indication of peer-review processes or reflexive discussion on what constitutes ‘quality’ research.

2.3. Opportunities

- **Fostering Researcher Development:** A new model can better support researchers' career progression, especially in under-recognised areas such as collaborative, practice-based, or societal research.
- **Innovation and Inclusion:** Creating new assessment tools (e.g., narrative CVs, open peer feedback, impact narratives) should help us foster inclusion and innovation, and recognise the complexity of research work.
- **Interdisciplinary and Societal Impact Recognition:** Expanding criteria can help reward activities central to Blanquerna’s mission—engaged, transformative research in education, health, and communication.

2.4. Threats

- *Resistance to Reform:* Shifting away from long-established metric-based assessment may face cultural or political resistance, especially from researchers who benefit from the current model.
- *Credibility Gaps:* Without robust communication and legitimacy-building efforts, the new system may be perceived as less objective or more discretionary.
- *Loss of Benchmarking Ease:* Moving from metric-based scores to qualitative evaluation may hinder comparisons at the institutional or external levels unless new tools are developed.

3. Synthesis of the Assessment

The current system at Blanquerna combines administrative robustness and historical continuity with a strong emphasis on quantitative, metric-based assessment. While it ensures procedural consistency and aligns with traditional quality assurance standards, it underrepresents the full diversity of scholarly contributions. It rewards a narrow definition of excellence, primarily favouring high-impact publications and competitive funding, with limited sensitivity to disciplinary differences, career stages, or alternative forms of impact. These limitations pose risks to fairness, inclusivity, and innovation.

Moreover, while formative purposes were claimed to be crucial, the existing procedures, strategies, tools, and mechanisms have yielded limited evidence of how they promote researcher development.

Significant aspects of the Co-Ara principles proposed by Re-Ass have been absent from the research assessment practices (e.g. valuing qualitative assessment, peer review, narrative accounts, and a broader spectrum of research contributions). Considering the strengths mentioned above, we should exercise careful navigation of cultural resistance, institutional coherence, and methodological clarity. The results of the SWOT analysis and the current practices assessment led us to identify the main challenges the ReAss project should address:

- *Raising awareness of the Co-Ara principles as a new Assessment Culture:* We aim to transition from quantification and rankings to reflective, qualitative assessments. We knew that this transition required a profound cultural change and strategic engagement. Re-Ass training and dissemination strategies must carefully address these requirements.
- *Ensuring Fairness and Transparency:* Qualitative assessment methods must be clearly justified and consistently applied to ensure perceived fairness. We are already working on new templates that can appropriately replace the existing ones (see Annexes)
- *Accommodating Disciplinary and Career Diversity:* This was a non-solved challenge in the existing model and current practices. The Re-Ass new model should provide mechanisms to remain sensitive to different research profiles while preserving shared standards.

4. Re-Ass dimensions of change

We have established the following seven dimensions of change that will structure the strategies and actions to develop in the pilot:

1. Broadening the Conceptualisation of Research Quality

The new proposal will foster the problematisation of the concepts of research assessment and research quality by discussing the current systems' assumptions, strengths, and weaknesses, and by acknowledging diverse outputs and impact types, including community engagement, open science, interdisciplinary work, and knowledge transfer.

2. Embedding Qualitative, Narrative and Peer-Based Assessment

The new proposal will develop clear procedures and tools for qualitative, peer-based evaluation and introduce narrative CVs or portfolios tailored to Blanquerna's research fields.

3. Ensuring Researcher Development and Inclusivity Across Career Stages

The proposal will discuss with the researcher community at Blanquerna how to include flexible, transparent benchmarks that account for researcher development, support early-career researchers, and accommodate non-traditional trajectories. At the same time, this dimension will discuss ways to address the tension between team and collaborative research work and individual development by considering the research activity structures and roles at Blanquerna and URL.

4. Enhancing Reflexivity, Transparency and Formative Feedback

Similarly, the proposal will provide procedures to ensure formative feedback, dialogic assessment practices, and clear criteria to ensure legitimacy and trust.

5. Fostering Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation

Ultimately, the proposal will sustain ongoing consultation and training with researchers to co-create the new criteria and raise awareness of the rationale behind the reform.

6. Reframing the Role of Assessment in Career Progression

Though this is a long-term dimension of change that exceeds the Re-Ass objectives, we also want to start the discussion regarding how assessment outcomes influence recognition, research time allocation, and promotion within a framework consistent with CoARA.

7. Aligning Individual and Group-Based Assessment to Support Sustainable Research Environments

Addressing the tension between individual performance evaluation and collective research practices by recognising collaborative roles, team science, and shared responsibility for research quality, with the aim of fostering resilient and sustainable research ecosystems.

8. Annex

8.1. Annex 1. Call for applications

Evaluation of FPCEE Faculty Research

Period assessed: from 1 October 2019 to 30 September 2022

The evaluation of research activity among academic staff who have a portion of their appointment recognised as research time, is an important tool for stimulating this activity among academic staff, for improving research strategies in professional development, and at the same time for maintaining the qualitative and quantitative standards by which we are assessed as a university centre by quality agencies.

It is in this context that, taking into account the previous call (2019) and the basic parameters published in Programme 7 of the FPCEE's General Research and Doctoral Plan, the current 2022 Call is hereby published. "Assessment of the Teaching Staff's Research Activity", in which the research activity for the period from 1 October 2019 to 30 September 2022 will be assessed.

To this end, the assessment will be mandatory for all FPCEE academic staff whose contracts include research, and voluntary for all other contracted academic staff. In all cases, a form must be completed and submitted by **4 May 2023** with the research activity data for the specified period, and the tables with the corresponding evidence must be attached. The following teaching staff are exempt from the assessment, even if they have a research-focused appointment, provided they meet one of the following conditions:

- a) That they have received a favourable decision on the recognition of a research period within the last 3 years (and that at least one of the years assessed falls within this period).
- b) That they have defended their doctoral thesis within a period of two years or less.
- c) That they have received a positive research or advanced research accreditation from any quality assessment agency of the national or international university system during the period assessed.

Exempt academic staff must complete the first section of the form (personal details), specify which of the three scenarios applies to them and attach the relevant certification. As you will see in the form, a new quantitative evaluation format based on three categories is proposed: publications, projects, and other merits. For this reason, even if you are exempt, we recommend that you complete it in order to provide a good metric of our research and to receive feedback that is more closely aligned with the faculty's overall situation.

For each category in the form, the quantitative value of the listed parameters must be determined based on the number of pieces of evidence available. Additionally, at the end of the form, tables containing the necessary data to identify each piece of evidence must be attached. Below is a table showing all the parameters and their associated metrics:

CATEGORIA	PARÀMETRES	MÈTRICA	
PUBLICATIONS	A1	Publicació WoS (JCR) Q1/Q2	Num. publicacions
		Publicació Scopus (SJR) Q1/Q2	Num. publicacions
		Publicació WoS (JCR) Q3/Q4	Num. publicacions
		Publicació Scopus (SJR) Q3/Q4	Num. publicacions
		Publicació Emerging /AHCI	Num. publicacions
	A2	Llibre SPI (Q1 estatal) (Q1/Q2 extranjeru)	Num. publicacions
		Capítol de llibre SPI (Q1 estatal) (Q1/Q2 extranger)	Num. capítols
	A3	Altres publicacions indexades	Num. publicacions
		Altres publicacions no indexades	Num. publicacions
		Altres llibres/ capítols de llibre	Num. capítols
		Comunicació/article congrés internacional	Num. comunicacions/artícles
		Revisor articles a revistes indexades	Num. articles/congressos
		Comitè científic congressos	Num. congressos
		Consell editorial revistes científiques	Num. revistes
	PROJECTES	B	IP Projecte competitiu + 20.000€
IP Projecte competitiu - 20.000€			Num. projectes
IP Projecte no competitiu/ transferència + 20.000€			Num. projectes
IP Projecte no competitiu/ transferència - 20.000€			Num. projectes
Participació projecte competitiu			Num. projectes
Participació projecte no competitiu/transferència			Num. projectes
IP de propostes no concedides a conv. competitives			Num. projectes
ALTRES MÉRITS	C	Tesis doctoral defensada (co-direcció x 0.5)	Num. tesis
		Patent o model d'utilitat	Num. patents
		Estada de recerca (mínim 1 més)	SI/NO
		IP grup SGR finançat	SI/NO
		IP grup SGR no finançat	SI/NO
		IP grup URL	SI/NO
		Membre Equip Directiu	Anys dins el període

We recommend that you first fill in the fields of the [template](#) (there is a tab for each section of the form and this [guide](#) will help you with the publications section), and finally complete the [form](#), with the quantitative data. Remember to first make a copy of the template, rename the file (SURNAME, FIRSTNAME), and then fill it in and upload it to the final section of the form.

This new evaluation tool is conceived as a complementary instrument to the assessment carried out by university quality evaluation agencies, since, while fully aligned with the indicators they propose, it serves as an element of self-evaluation that will allow the achievement of the research objectives defined for each professional category to be validated at any time. Nevertheless, accountability to the FPCEE will continue to be reported on a triennial basis.

8.3. Annex 3. Table completion guide

PAUTES PER EMPLENAR LA TAULA A1: ARTICLES A WOS (JCR) - SCOPUS (SJR)

Com trobar les dades a JCR?

- Per consultar el JCR feu clic [aquí](#).
- Busqueu la revista pel títol o l'ISSN.
- Un cop l'heu trobada heu de seleccionar l'any en que va sortir publicat l'article (1), l'edició del JCR (SCI, SSCI, AHCI i ESCI) (2) i el quartil en que es troba la revista (Q1, Q2, Q3 o Q4) (3).

En cas que estigui a més d'una categoria, indiqueu la que més us beneficiï.

Com trobar les dades a SJR?

- Per consultar el SJR feu clic [aquí](#).
- Busqueu la revista pel títol o l'ISSN.
- Un cop l'heu trobada heu de consultar l'any en que va sortir publicat l'article i el quartil (Q1, Q2, Q3 o Q4) en que es troba la revista.

En cas que estigui a més d'una categoria, indiqueu la que més us beneficiï.

PAUTES PER EMPLENAR LA TAULA A2: LLIBRES I CAPÍTOLS

Com trobar les dades a SPI?

- Per consultar l'SPI feu clic [aquí](#).
- Aneu a l'apartat resultats (1) i consulteu l'any de la classificació general (2) més proper a l'any de publicació del llibre.
 - Per exemple, en el cas d'un llibre publicat l'any 2022 heu de consultar l'edició de 2022. Per anys anteriors heu de consultar l'edició del 2018.
- Un cop esteu a la classificació general trobareu dos llistats d'editorials (estats i estrangers) (3).
- A continuació heu de buscar l'editorial i la posició que ocupa dins del llistat (4).
 - Per exemple, un llibre de l'editorial Pirámide publicat al 2022 ocupa la posició 5 de 99.

Resultados 1

2012 — Clasificación General

2014 — Clasificación General

2018 — Clasificación General

2 2022 — Clasificación General

Prestigio de las editoriales según expertos españoles **Clasificación general 2022**

Editoriales españolas 3			Editoriales extranjeras		
Posición	Editorial	ICEE General	Posición	Editorial	ICEE General
1	Tirant lo Blanch (Grupo editorial Tirant lo Blanch)	1090	1	Oxford University Press	1043
2	Aranzadi (Aranzadi LA LEY / Karmov Group)	760	2	Routledge (Taylor & Francis Group)	1026
3	Dybbach	758	3	Cambridge University Press	1020
4	McGraw Hill	541	4	Springer	950
5	Alianza (Grupo Anaya, Hachette Livre)	530	5	Elsevier	407
6	Pirámide (Grupo Anaya, Hachette Livre)	530	6	McGraw Hill	405
6	Cátedra (Grupo Anaya, Hachette Livre)	525			

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8.4. Annex 4. Scoring table

CATEGORIA	ACTIVITAT	MÈTRICA	VALOR MÀXIM		TOPALL	
PRODUCCIÓ	A1	Publicació WoS (JCR) Q1/Q2	Num. publicacions	10	No	60
		Publicació Scopus (SJR) Q1/Q2	Num. publicacions	8	No	
		Publicació WoS (JCR) Q3/Q4	Num. publicacions	6	No	
		Publicació Scopus (SJR) Q3/Q4	Num. publicacions	4	No	
		Publicació emergent	Num. publicacions	3	6	
	A2	Llibre SPI (Q1 estatal) (Q1/Q2 extranjer)	Num. publicacions	6	12	
		Capítol de llibre SPI (Q1 estatal) (Q1/Q2 extranjer)	Num. capítols	4	12	
	A3	Altres publicacions indexades	Num. publicacions	2	4	
		Altres publicacions no indexades	Num. publicacions	1	2	
		Altres llibres/ capítols de llibre	Num. capítols	1	2	
		Comunicació/article congres internacional	Num.comunicacions/articles	1	No	
		Revisor articles a revistes o congressos	Num.articles/congressos	0,5	3	
		Comité científic congressos	Num. congressos	0'5	1	
Consell editorial revistes científiques		Num. revistes	0'5	1		
PROJECTES	B	IP Projecte competitiu + 20.000€	Num. projectes	10	20	30
		IP Projecte competitiu - 20.000€	Num. projectes	8	16	
		IP Projecte no competitiu/ transferència + 20.000€	Num. projectes	8	16	
		IP Projecte no competitiu/ transferència - 20.000€	Num. projectes	6	12	
		Participació projecte competitiu	Num .projectes	4	12	
		Participació projecte no competitiu/transferència	Num. projectes	3	9	
		Preparació propostes no concedides a conv. competitives	Num. projectes	1	2	
MÈRITS	C	Tesis doctoral defensada (co-direcció x 0.5)	Num. tesis	5	15	10
		Patent o model d'utilitat	Num.patents	5	10	
		Estada de recerca (mínim 1 més)	SI/NO	3	3	
		IP grup SGR finançat	SI/NO	3	3	
		IP grup SGR no finançat	SI/NO	2	2	
		IP grup URL	SI/NO	1	1	

Nota: Acreditar vinculació a equip directiu durant el període avaluat suposarà un increment en la puntuació final de 5 punts per any acreditat.

Annex 5. Final scoring thresholds

	Puntuació																				
	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100
Associat																					
Contractat Doctor																					
Ajudant Doctor																					
Titular 30																					
Titular 38																					
Catedràtic																					

5.6. Annex 6. Individual evaluation report template

Benvolgut XXX,

Vista la informació que vas lliurar en resposta a la convocatòria d'avaluació de la recerca del professorat de la FPCEE del període comprès entre l'1 d'octubre del 2019 i el 30 de setembre del 2022, t'informem:

- Has tret un **53,5** sobre 100 punts. La teva categoria professional, **Ajudant Doctor**, ha obtingut una mitjana de 82,6 punts. Aquesta ha oscil·lat entre un mínim de 53,5 i un màxim de 93.

Per determinar aquests valors hem aplicat una taula de puntuació de les evidències per cada paràmetre, amb uns topalls per categoria. Així doncs, i atenent als barems establerts per cada categoria professional et notifiquem que has obtingut una valoració final:

Favorable.

Validació de les dades i aclariments

Per altra banda, i al efectes de poder fer les correccions oportunes, des de biblioteca i recerca, et fem saber que hem detectat algunes errades al formulari, que detallam:

*Nombre de publicacions WoS (JCR) en el quartil Q3/Q4 on vares contestar 3, calia contestar 0.
Nombre de publicacions Scopus (SJR) en el quartil Q3/Q4 on vares contestar 1, calia contestar 2.*

Nombre de Publicacions indexades a Emerging Sources Citation Index o Arts and Humanities Citation Index. on vares contestar 0, calia contestar 4.

Comunicació/article en congrés internacional on vares contestar 5, calia contestar 6.

Revisor d'articles en revistes científiques o congressos internacionals on vares contestar 4, calia contestar 3.

Membre de comitè científic de congressos on vares contestar 2, calia contestar 3.

Per clarificar aquests aspectes o altres dubtes que puguis plantejar, pots contactar a partir de l'1 de setembre de 2023:

- Per tot el referent a la categoria de publicacions pots dirigir-te a Biblioteca (bca_fpcee_recerca@blanquerna.url.edu)
- Respecte a la de projectes, tesis o altres mèrits a l'oficina de recerca (oficinarecercafpee@blanquerna.url.edu).

Et recordem que l'octubre del 2025 es tornarà a convocar l'avaluació de recerca d'un nou període.